

A guide to selecting high-performing renewable antibodies for Alpha-Dystroglycan across western blot and immunoprecipitation

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Method

The standardized protocols used for this antibody characterization study were established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers, and antibody manufacturers (1). Brief descriptions of the experimental procedures used in this study are described below.

Cell lines

The cell lines used in this study are listed in Table 1. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) (2). All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Primary and secondary antibodies

Primary antibodies are listed in Table 2 with RRIDs (3). Working dilutions for western blot and immunofluorescence, and volumes corresponding to 2 µg input for immunoprecipitation, are provided in Table 3. Secondary antibodies and their working concentrations are listed in Table 4. Antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios.

Antibody screening by western blot on culture medium

HAP1 WT and *DAG1* KO cells were washed 3x with PBS 1x and starved for ~36 hrs. Culture media were collected and centrifuged for 10 min at 500 x *g* to eliminate cells and larger contaminants, then for 10 min at 4500 x *g* to eliminate smaller contaminants. Culture media were then concentrated by centrifuging at

4000 x *g* for 30min using the Amicon Ultra-15 Centrifugal Filter Units with a membrane NMWL of 10kDa (MilliporeSigma cat. number UFC901024). Culture media were finally supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated with the membrane in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture medium

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg of antibody to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 87788 in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10004D). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

Culture medium from HAP1 WT was collected as described in the western section above. 0.5 mL aliquots at 1.0 mg/mL of culture medium were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 mL of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels.

References

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC000120c013	CVCL_SK29	HAP1	<i>DAG1</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the Alpha-Dystroglycan antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab106110*	1117846-1	AB_10861354	monoclonal	2238	mouse	0.10	Wb

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, *= monoclonal antibody

Table 3: Dilutions of Alpha-Dystroglycan antibodies used in all western blot and immunoprecipitation

Company	Catalog number	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)	Vendor- recommended Wb dilution	Wb dilution used	IP volume (μL , for 2 μg input)
Abcam	ab106110*	0.10	1/100	1/100	20.0

Table 4: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)	Working concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.5
Thermo Fisher Scientific	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse IgM Antibody	31440	AB_228329	polyclonal	0.8	0.4

Table 5: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

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Figure 1: Alpha-Dystroglycan antibody screening by western blot on culture medium

Figure 2: Alpha-Dystroglycan antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture medium

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: Alpha-Dystroglycan antibody screening by western blot on culture medium.

Lysates from HAP1 WT and *DAG1* KO were prepared and analyzed in western blot using the indicated Alpha-Dystroglycan antibodies. Ponceau-stained membranes are shown to confirm equal loading and efficient protein transfer from gel to membrane. Predicted band size: 97.4 kDa. *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: Alpha-Dystroglycan antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture medium.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using the indicated Alpha-Dystroglycan antibodies. Immunoprecipitates were analyzed by western blot using the Alpha-Dystroglycan antibody ab234587 (1/500). Ponceau-stained membranes are shown. SM=6% starting material; UB=6% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate, HC= antibody heavy chain, LC= antibody light chain. *= monoclonal antibody.